

Second Order Conductivity Probes a Cascade of Singularities in a Moiré Superlattice

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Systems lacking inversion symmetry inherently demonstrate a nonlinear electrical response (NLER) to an applied electric bias, emerging through extrinsic mechanisms. This response is highly sensitive to the electronic band structure, which can be engineered with remarkable precision in moiré superlattices formed from atomically thin quantum materials. Moiré superlattices host complex Fermi surface reconstructions near van Hove singularities (vHSs) in the electronic density of states. However, the role of these reconstructions in shaping NLER remains insufficiently understood. In this work, we systematically explore NLER in moiré superlattices of twisted double bilayer graphene (tDBLG) by tuning the Fermi level across multiple moiré bands on both sides of the charge neutrality point. We observe sharp variations and sign reversals in the NLER appearing via extrinsic pathways near mid-band vHSs. The second-order conductivity close to the vHSs demonstrates a much higher value than previous reports of extrinsic NLER in any other material. Our results demonstrate that NLER can serve as a sensitive probe of Fermi surface reconstructions and establish tDBLG as a versatile and highly efficient platform for generating and controlling the nonlinear electrical response.

The Fermi surface topology profoundly influences the electronic properties of materials [1], especially near the critical points [2] of electronic bands, where drastic changes to the topology/connectivity of the Fermi surface—Lifshitz transitions [3–6]—occur. These not only lead to a divergent density of states (DoS) or van Hove singularities (vHS) but also dramatically alter the velocity and effective mass of the charge carriers. While the Fermi energy (E_F) can be precisely tuned in atomically thin quantum materials, [7] vHSs in such systems are often located at electronically inaccessible energies ($E_F > 1$ eV), as in single-layer (SLG) [8] and bilayer (BLG) [9] graphene, or at the band edge, as in BLG [10,11]. However, in the case of moiré superlattices, the vHSs can be tuned to appear at intermediate energies by choosing a suitable inter-layer twist angle [12–15]. Several exotic phenomena can co-exist near the vHSs in moiré superlattices. For example, a strong orbital angular moment in SLG-hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) [16], superconductivity in non-magic-angle SLG-SLG [17] and BLG-BLG moiré patterns [18], correlated [14,15,19] and magnetically [6,20] ordered states, etc. Identifying and understanding vHSs are crucial to exploiting these novel states of matter appearing in artificial materials.

The vHSs in moiré superlattices can be identified using first-order electronic transport measurement only under time-reversal symmetry broken condition by means of the

Hall conductivity [14,15]. Recently, it has been demonstrated that the second-order nonlinear electrical response (NLER) [21–27] is highly sensitive to the electronic band structure [28–34] and to the Fermi surface topology [34–36] in the absence of time-reversal symmetry breaking. The NLER arises by virtue of the intrinsic Berry curvature dipole (BCD) [30,33,36–39] and/or by disorder-mediated extrinsic side-jump and skew scattering [24,28,29,40,41]. The extrinsic mechanisms only require inversion symmetry breaking and are strongly dependent on the effective mass and nature of the charge carriers [24,28], both of which show immense modulation as E_F is tuned across the vHSs. Multiple experimental observations of intrinsic and extrinsic NLER in moiré superlattices have been reported [28,29,32,33]. However, the influence of vHSs on NLER, and whether NLER arising purely from extrinsic mechanisms can reliably detect vHSs in moiré superlattices, remain uncertain. Further experimental studies are needed to explore how NLER evolves near vHSs, particularly in engineered superlattices where multiple vHSs can be precisely tuned to appear within accessible Fermi energy ranges.

In this study, we explore NLER in ABAB-stacked twisted double bilayer graphene (tDBLG) moiré superlattices with low interlayer twist angles (θ). By leveraging the small superlattice Brillouin zone, we modulate the Fermi level (E_F) up to fourth superlattice bands, *i.e.*, more than three

FIG. 1. Device geometry and evidence of vHS in first-order electronic transport: **a**, Schematic of the device and the measurement circuit. The inset shows the cross-section of the tDBLG channel. **b**, Optical image of the device with $2\mu\text{m}$ scalebar. **c**, R_S vs D characteristics at $n = 0$ indicating the topological change in the band structure. **d**, $n - D$ contour plot of R_S . The R_S maxima at integer superlattice fillings are marked with vertical dashed lines. **e**, R_S vs n characteristics at $D = 0$. The integer fillings are marked with arrows. **f**, $n - D$ contour plot of V_H^ω . **g**, V_H^ω vs n data at $D = 0$. The sign changes close to the integer values of n/n_s are marked with black arrows; the sign changes at non-integer values are marked with brown arrows.

times the superlattice filling density (n_s) on both sides of the charge neutrality point (CNP). We identify the mid-band vHSs by measuring the Hall resistance as a function of the vertical displacement field (D) and carrier concentration (n). We demonstrate that NLER changes signs close to all mid-band vHSs. Furthermore, the second-order conductivity ($\sigma^{2\omega}$) becomes pronounced close to the mid gap vHSs in the second and higher superlattice bands reaching a magnitude of $70 \mu\text{mV}^{-1}\Omega^{-1}$, a value one order of magnitude higher than any previous report [27,28]. The temperature (T) dependent scaling behavior of the NLER close to the vHSs confirms that the observed second-order response is dominated by a combination of extrinsic-side jump and skew scattering mechanisms. Our study establishes NLER as a valuable tool for locating vHSs under time-reversal symmetric condition. Moreover, the mid-band vHSs at higher superlattice bands represent an efficient and tunable platform to generate NLER.

Encapsulated ABAB-stacked dual-gated tDBLG field effect transistor was fabricated using the usual tear and stack method [42] and dry transfer technique [43,44]. See methods and supporting information (SI) section 1 for fabrication and device details. We measured three samples, namely, A, B, and C having different θ (See SI section 1 for estimation of θ). In the main text we focus on the data from sample A. Fig. 1a presents the device schematic and circuit diagram used for the simultaneous acquisition of first and second-harmonic longitudinal ($V_{xx}^\omega, V_{xx}^{2\omega}$) and

transverse ($V_{xy}^\omega, V_{xy}^{2\omega}$) voltage drops. Inset schematically shows the cross-section of the channel; individual layers including the θ deg twisted BLG layers are marked. An optical image of the device with $2\mu\text{m}$ scalebar is shown in Fig. 1b. Fig. 1c shows the sheet resistance R_S as a function of the vertical displacement field (D) measured at $T = 2\text{K}$, at $n = 0$. We tune n and D independently by simultaneously controlling the top (V_{tg}) and bottom (V_{bg}) gate voltages (see Methods). See SI section 2 for mobility calculations. The electronic band structure in tDBLG can be substantially tuned by D [45,46,42,47] unlike in tBLG moiré superlattices. The resistance sharply increases beyond $|D|/\epsilon_0 > 0.15 \text{ V nm}^{-1}$, marking a topological phase transition in the band structure, which is a characteristic feature of tDBLG [36,47]. The $n - D$ contour plot of the R_S presented in Fig. 1d further elucidates the electronic band structure of our tDBLG sample. We observe the charge neutrality point (CNP) at $n = 0$. Additionally, we observe resistance maxima at various positive and negative n . The high resistance states corresponding to integer band fillings appearing at $n \approx \pm 1.1, \pm 2.2, \pm 3.3 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, are marked as dashed vertical lines [46]. Clearly, these values correspond to integer multiples of $n_s = 4/A \approx \pm 1.1 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, carrier concentration of one completely filled superlattice band. Here, $A \approx \sqrt{3}a^2/(2\theta^2)$ is the area of the moiré unit cell, and a is graphene's lattice parameter [42,48]. From these expressions we calculate a twist angle $\theta \approx 0.7^\circ$

FIG. 2. **Second-order nonlinear transport in tDBLG:** **a**, The top panel shows $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ vs n data at different values of I_{ds}^ω at $D = -0.125 \text{ Vnm}^{-1}$. The bottom (middle) panel shows normalized $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}/I_{ds}^2$ vs n data at different I_{ds}^ω , collapsing on each other. **b**, $|V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}|$ vs I_{ds}^ω at $n \approx 0.5$ is shown as green (blue) data points. The solid traces are parabolic fits. **c**, Schematic of the two measurement configurations with switched polarities of voltage and current probes. **d**, The red and the black traces are the data at two measurement configurations. The top middle and bottom panels show the n -dependence of R_s , $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$, and $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$, respectively, at $D = -0.025 \text{ Vnm}^{-1}$.

Importantly, the R_s maxima consistently appear in the same positions throughout the channel (see SI section 4), which excludes the possibility that a high twist-angle anomaly is responsible for the multiple peaks observed in R_s . For convenience, we describe the carrier density in units of n_s in the following discussions. R_s vs n data at $D = 0 \text{ V nm}^{-1}$ is presented in Fig. 1e. The R_s peaks at integer values of n/n_s are marked with black arrows. R_s maxima at all integer band fillings ($n/n_s = 0$ to ± 4) has been previously observed in tDBLG at $\theta \lesssim 1^\circ$. [46] At $\pm n_s$, we observe the closing of the first moiré gap at high $|D|$, consistent with earlier reports [18,45–47,49,50]. The R_s maxima $\pm 2n_s$ is not expected from single particle band structure calculation but can appear due to electron-electron

correlation [46]. Also see SI section 4 for data from another sample (sample B) with a different $\theta \approx 1.4^\circ$ twist angle.

Fig. 1f presents the $n - D$ contour plot of the Hall voltage (V_H^ω) at 500 mT magnetic field (B_\perp) with constant source-drain current $I_{ds}^\omega = 200 \text{ nA}$. The data demonstrate abrupt sign reversals in V_H^ω at $n/n_s \approx 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3$, indicating a change in the carrier type changes from hole to electron when n/n_s is varied through the integer band fillings. The V_H^ω vs n/n_s characteristic at $D = 0$ is presented in Fig. 1g. In addition to those at integer n/n_s , we also observe the sign reversals of V_H^ω at non-integer values of n/n_s , which can be attributed to the vHSs. The existence of the vHSs in the density of states of the SLG or BLG moiré superlattices are well known [12–15]. They are accompanied by the Lifshitz transitions where the topology/connectivity of the Fermi surface changes [51]. Such changes substantially modify the group velocity and effective mass of the charge carriers. Here, the nature of the charge carriers changes from electron-like to hole-like when the E_F is increased through these reconstructions in the Fermi surface. Thus, the vHSs can be detected using the V_H^ω [14]. The first order transport (V_{xx}^ω) under time-reversal symmetric condition is insensitive to the vHSs, in our experimental conditions. However, when time-reversal symmetry is broken, i.e., in presence of vertical magnetic field, the vHSs lead to sign reversal in the first order transport (V_H^ω) [14,15,18,51]. See SI section 5 for Hall data from sample B ($\theta \approx 1.4^\circ$) showing tunable vHSs.

We now focus on the second order nonlinear electrical response (NLER) under time-reversal symmetry preserved condition [24,28]. NLER is a general property of any system with broken inversion symmetry and arises due to the non-zero elements of nonlinear conductivity tensor [40]. In the moiré systems, it is the interlayer twist that breaks the inversion symmetry and produces NLER, which has been previously reported on moiré superlattices based on SLG [28,29,33,35]. The NLER induces voltage drops at the second harmonic, or 2ω frequency, either parallel ($V_{xx}^{2\omega}$) and/or perpendicular ($V_{xy}^{2\omega}$) to the applied current bias (I_{ds}^ω). We present the $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ vs n data at $D = -0.125 \text{ Vnm}^{-1}$ for different values of I_{ds}^ω ranging from 30 to 200 nA in the top panel of Fig. 2a. See SI section 3 for the $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ data. The middle (bottom) panel of Fig. 2a shows the normalized $V_{xx(y)}^{2\omega}/I_{ds}^2$ vs n data. Despite a low signal to noise ratio at low values of I_{ds}^ω , normalized $V_{xx(y)}^{2\omega}/I_{ds}^2$ data are observed to collapse on each other for the entire range of n , indicating a proportionality relationship $V_{xx(y)}^{2\omega} \propto I_{ds}^{\omega 2}$. To further elucidate this, we present the $|V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}|$ vs I_{ds}^ω data at $n \approx 0.5 n_s$ as blue (green) data

FIG. 3. $n - D$ dependent evolution of NLER, observation of sign reversal near vHSs: **a**, $n - D$ contour plot of $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$. The changes in $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ at the integer and non-integer n/n_s are indicated with black and brown arrows, respectively **b**, $n - D$ contour plot of $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ is presented. **c**, The top (bottom) panel demonstrates n dependence of V_H^ω and R_S ($V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ and $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ in time reversal symmetry preserved condition) at $D = 0.175 \text{ Vnm}^{-1}$. **d**, The same data at $D = -0.025 \text{ Vnm}^{-1}$ is presented. V_H^ω changes sign at the vHSs (indicated with an arrow). Both $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ and $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ changes sign in the vicinity of vHS.

points, in Fig. 2b. The solid traces represent parabolic fits. Additionally, we measured the $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}$ in two different measurement configurations, reversing the polarity of the voltage and current probes [25]. The two configurations are schematically illustrated in Fig. 2c and highlighted in black and red. The polarity of the electrodes are indicated with + and - symbols. The top panel of Fig. 2d presents the $R_S - n$ data at $D = -0.025 \text{ Vnm}^{-1}$ measured in the two configurations, showing a perfect overlap. The middle (bottom) panel presents the $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}$ vs n data, which shows opposite signs for the two different measurement configurations (measured at $I_{ds}^\omega = 200 \text{ nA}$). Notably both the $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ and $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ (i) show qualitatively and quantitatively similar variations with n , (ii) follow the proportionality relation $V_{xx(y)}^{2\omega} \propto I_{ds}^{\omega 2}$. (iii) change sign when the measurement configuration is changed. These observations rule out any significant contribution of thermal effects in the measured $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}$ signal. Additionally, they also indicate the extrinsic mechanism arising from static and/or dynamic disorders as a primary contributor to the observed NLER across the entire n range in our tDBLG sample [24,28,29].

$V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}$ demonstrates strong variations as a function of n , indicating its sensitivity to the electronic structure of tDBLG. Interestingly, the sign change in the NLER is observed at $n/n_s \approx 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3$, reflecting the transition of the carriers from holes to electrons. Such sign changes at integer fillings have been previously observed in moiré superlattices of SLG-hBN [28] and tBLG. [29] The additional sign changes observed at non-integer values of n/n_s in NLER data indicate the presence of finer features in the band structures that are difficult to observe in the first order transport under time-reversal symmetric conditions.

To elucidate the origin of these sign changes in the NLER at non-integer n/n_s we investigate the $n - D$ contour plots of $V_{xx(y)}^{2\omega}$ which is presented in Fig. 3a (b). The diagonally dispersing features, appearing at fixed V_{bg} are attributed to a contact effect arising from the non-top gated regions. The contour plots unambiguously demonstrate sign changes in the NLER in the vicinity of integer values of n/n_s , across all values of D , which is indicated with black arrows. The sign changes at non-integer n/n_s are marked with brown arrows. The $n - D$ contour plots of $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ and $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ are observed to be qualitatively similar. The locus of

FIG. 4. Giant second-order conductivity near vHSs: **a (b)**, The $n - D$ contour plot of longitudinal (transverse) second order conductivity is presented. **c**, The top (bottom) panels present $\sigma_{xxx}^{2\omega}$ ($\sigma_{yxx}^{2\omega}$) vs n data at a few D , indicated as horizontal dashed lines. $\sigma_{xxx}^{2\omega}$ ($\sigma_{yxx}^{2\omega}$) becomes pronounced close to the vHSs.

the sign changes at the non-integer n/n_s observed in $V_{xx(y)}^{2\omega}$ closely match those observed in V_H^ω (Fig. 1f). To further highlight this, we compare $V_{xx(y)}^{2\omega}$ with V_H^ω and R_s at a few different D and n . The top (bottom) panel of Fig. 3c present the n -dependence of V_H^ω and R_s ($V_{xx(y)}^{2\omega}$) at $D = 0.175 \text{ V nm}^{-1}$ around $n/n_s = 2.5$. The location of the vHS giving rise to the sign change in V_H^ω is marked with the arrow $n \approx 2.5$. Notably, both $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ and $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ demonstrate sign changes in the vicinity of the vHS.

Likewise, the n dependences of V_H^ω , R_s , $V_{xx(y)}^{2\omega}$ at $D = -0.025 \text{ V nm}^{-1}$ (Fig. 3d) demonstrate the sign change of NLER close to the vHS at $n/n_s = 0.5$. The second-order conductivity [23,24] is significantly influenced by the electronic band structure [28,29,31–33], through Berry curvature (Ω) [21,30,33,36] and topology of the Fermi surface [35,36] and electronic bands [36]. Typically, the sign of intrinsic BCD contribution to NLER is proportional to the sign of Ω , which is reverses, when the D is inverted [33,34], contrary to our observations. The sign changes in NLER are consistently observed in topologically trivial electronic bands of tDBG at $D = 0$ [47,46] excluding the topological phase transitions as its origin. The Fermi surface topology is particularly important for extrinsic NLER assisted by impurity scattering, which is unavoidable at the Fermi surface. NLER is related to the Fermi distribution function's first and second derivatives [23], whose signs flip when the Fermi surface experiences a Lifshitz transition near the locations of vHSs. Our This can as a sign reversal in the nonlinear electrical response (NLER) in the vicinity of the vHSs. Our experiment demonstrates that the NLER, under time-reversal symmetric conditions, is a sensitive probe for detecting mid-band vHSs emerging at non-integer values of n/n_s in moiré superlattices. To the understand the reproducibility of the observed effect, we present the NLER data from a different channel region of sample A in the SI section 4. Additionally, the NLER and V_H^ω data from samples B ($\theta \approx 1.4^\circ$) and C ($\theta \approx 0.8^\circ$) are presented in the see SI section 5 and 6, respectively. Data from different samples qualitatively agrees and demonstrates sign changes in NLER close to the vHSs, within sample-to-sample variations.

The second order current density in response to first order applied bias is given by $j_a^{2\omega} = \sigma_{abc}^{2\omega} E_b^\omega E_c^\omega$ [24]. Here E^ω is the applied first order bias. a, b, c are indices for axes. The $\sigma^{2\omega}$ is the second order conductivity, a fundamental property of the material independent of applied bias or sample dimensions. Fig. 4a(b) shows the second-order longitudinal (transverse) conductivity extracted as $\sigma_{xxx}^{2\omega}$ ($\sigma_{yxx}^{2\omega}$) = $\sigma V_{xx}^{2\omega} L/V_{xx}^{\omega^2}$ ($\sigma V_{xy}^{2\omega} L/V_{xx}^{\omega^2} \times L^2/W$) [28] as a function of n and D . Here L , W and σ are the length, and width of the channel and first order conductivity, respectively (also see SI section 9). The second-order conductivity is observed to vary from a high negative to a high positive value in the vicinity of the mid-gap vHS. The analytical expressions previously derived by Z. Du *et al.* [24] highlight $\sigma^{2\omega} \propto q^3 m^*$ dependence (q and m^* are the charge and the effective mass of the carriers, respectively), making the sign of $\sigma^{2\omega}$ dependent on the sign of q , which changes at the vHSs and also at integer n/n_s . Additionally, the electron-electron correlation in the moiré superlattices can lead to a divergent m^* close to vHSs

FIG. 5. **T dependent scaling behavior of NLER close to vHS** : **a**, The bottom panels presents the R_s vs n data at different T ranging from 2 to 10 K at $D = 0$. The top and bottom panels present the $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ and $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ vs n data at different temperatures. The brown arrows indicate the sign change in the $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ and $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ in the vicinity of the vHSs. **b**, The top left (right) panels presents $R_s^2 V_{xy}^{2\omega} V_{xx}^{\omega^2} / V_{xx}^{\omega^2}$ vs. R_s data at $n/n_s = 0.7$ marked with black (red) arrow. The similar data at $n/n_s = 1.9$ is presented in the bottom panels. The dotted lines indicate the fits using the generalized scaling behavior.

giving rise to a massive $\sigma^{2\omega}$. Interestingly, the values of both $\sigma_{xxx}^{2\omega}$ and $\sigma_{yxx}^{2\omega}$ have the same order of magnitudes, indicating they originate from the extrinsic mechanisms [28]. We show the $\sigma_{xxx}^{2\omega}$ ($\sigma_{yxx}^{2\omega}$) vs n data at two different-values of D in the top (bottom) panels of Fig. 4c. We observe giant second order conductivity in the second and higher superlattice bands. For example, at $D/\varepsilon_0 = 0$ V nm $^{-1}$, we achieve $|\sigma_{yxx}^{2\omega}| \approx 70$ $\mu\text{mV}^{-1}\Omega^{-1}$ near the mid-band vHS ($n/n_s \approx -1.7$) of the second superlattice valance band. The observed $\sigma^{2\omega}$ is almost one order of magnitude higher than any previously reported value at $D = 0$ arising via intrinsic [32,33,36] or extrinsic [28,29,35] pathways in any other material at similar T (SI section 7). NLER is often parameterized by second harmonic generation efficiency ($\eta = V_{xy}^{2\omega}/V_{xx}^{\omega^2}$) and responsivity ($\gamma = V_{xy}^{2\omega}/(R_{xx} I_{ds}^{\omega^2}) = R_{xx} V_{xy}^{2\omega}/V_{xx}^{\omega^2}$). Here, R_{xx} is the channel resistance. Experimentally observed values of η ($\approx 4 \times 10^3$ V $^{-1}$) and γ ($\approx 10^6$ V/W), are larger than any previous report on graphene-based moiré superlattices at $D = 0$ see (SI section 7). A NLER of such high figures-of-merit could pave the way for commercially viable and highly tunable rectifier devices [22,52].

The NLER in non-centrosymmetric crystals can appear from a combination of the extrinsic scattering mechanisms [24] and the intrinsic BCD dipole [21]. Extrinsic mechanisms lead to both transverse ($V_{xy}^{2\omega}$) and

longitudinal ($V_{xx}^{2\omega}$) NLER. Pure intrinsic BCD, requiring additional C_3 symmetry breaking, leads to only $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$. A similar qualitative and quantitative n -dependence of $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ and $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ (Figure 2) and absence of a D -dependent sign reversal [30,33,34] in $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$ (Figure 3) points towards a dominant extrinsic mechanism [28,29] in our samples. Moreover, our data fails to fit a linear $V_{xy}^{2\omega}/V_{xx}^{\omega^2}$ vs. σ^2 dependence commonly observed when dominant intrinsic mechanism is coupled with skew scattering [33,36,37]. (see SI section 8 and 10 for data from sample A and C, respectively) To understand the origin of the observed NLER in our sample, we investigate its T -dependent scaling behavior. Here, we use T as a tuning parameter for the scattering rates. In theory, the NLER is expected to follow a generalized scaling law given by [24]

$$R_s^2 \frac{V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}}{V_{xx}^{\omega^2}} = C_1 R_0^2 + C_2 R_0 R_T + C_3 R_T^2 \quad (1)$$

Here, $R_0 = R_s(T \rightarrow 0)$, and $R_T = R_s(T) - R_0$. C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 are the scaling parameters containing contributions from the intrinsic BCD (appearing only in $V_{xy}^{2\omega}$), side-jump and skew scattering from static and dynamic impurities [24]. See SI section 10 for more details. The bottom panel of Fig. 5a presents the $R_s - n$ data at different values of T , ranging from 2K to 10K at $D = 0$. The variation of $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}$ as a function of n , at the same values of T is presented in the top (middle) panel of Fig. 5a. The brown arrows indicate the sign changes in the NLER at the

non-integer values of n/n_s . We highlight the scaling behavior of the NLER at a few representative values of n/n_s (≈ 0.7 and 1.9 , indicated with black and red arrows), plotting the $R_s^2 V_{xy}^{2\omega}/V_{xx}^{\omega^2}$ vs R_s characteristic in Fig. 5b as red (black) data points. The top and bottom panels present the data at $n/n_s = 0.7$ and $n/n_s = 1.9$, respectively (black arrows in Fig. 5a). The dotted lines present the fits to the data using equation 1 (see SI Section 9 for data from sample C). The black (red) fits in top panels of Fig. 5b, yields the following values of \mathcal{C}_1 , \mathcal{C}_2 , and \mathcal{C}_3 , respectively: -89.8 ± 2.65 (-51.6 ± 2.71) V^{-1} , 305 ± 17.2 (211 ± 17.7) V^{-1} and -274 ± 23.5 (-205 ± 24.3) V^{-1} . All the parameters have the same order of magnitude, indicating the presence of the side-jump mechanism in addition to skew scattering from static and dynamic impurities. Likewise, from the black (red) fits in bottom panels of Fig. 5b, the following values of \mathcal{C}_1 , \mathcal{C}_2 , and \mathcal{C}_3 are obtained, respectively: 193 ± 12 (312 ± 18.5) V^{-1} , $-4.89 \times 10^3 \pm 6.33 \times 10^2$ ($-8.61 \times 10^3 \pm 9.5 \times 10^2$) V^{-1} and $3.47 \times 10^4 \pm 6.5 \times 10^3$ ($6.23 \times 10^4 \pm 9.8 \times 10^3$) V^{-1} . In this case, considering the large \mathcal{C}_3 , skew scattering is identified as the dominant mechanism. A dominant intrinsic contribution would lead to $\mathcal{C}_1:\mathcal{C}_2:\mathcal{C}_3 \approx 1:2:1$, a behavior absent [34] in our samples. An intricate theoretical understanding on how the contribution from different extrinsic mechanisms vary within a moiré band is still missing. A complex variation may lead to additional sign reversals of $\sigma^{2\omega}$ as a function of n . However, given the collective $\sigma^{2\omega} \propto q^3 m^*$ dependence of all extrinsic mechanisms, a sign reversal of overall $\sigma^{2\omega}$ close to the vHSs is expected, as observed in our experiment.

In conclusion, we performed simultaneous first and second order conductivity measurements on a moiré superlattice of twisted double bilayer graphene (tDBLG) by varying the Fermi energy across multiple superlattice bands on both sides of the CNP. We identified a cascade of mid-band singularities by performing Hall measurements at low magnetic fields. We demonstrate that under time-reversal symmetric condition, the nonlinear conductivity arising from a combination of extrinsic side-jump and skew scattering mechanism, changes sign while exhibiting local extrema close to the vHSs, over the whole range of the superlattice bands. Our study establishes the second-order conductivity as a valuable tool to identify vHSs under time-reversal symmetric preserved condition. We demonstrate giant extrinsic second-order conductivity close to the vHSs of second and higher superlattice bands with much higher value than previous reports in any other materials, at similar thermodynamic conditions. Our work cements vHSs in tDBLG to be a highly efficient and tunable platform to generate second-order nonlinear electrical response.

METHODS:

Device fabrication: The hBN and BLG crystals were individually exfoliated onto clean SiO_2 ($300 \text{ nm} \pm 5\%$) / p++-Si substrates. hBN flakes with thicknesses ranging from 15 to 40 nm were selected as encapsulation and dielectric layers. The heterostructures were assembled using the dry transfer method, employing the pickup and stack technique within an Ar-filled glovebox equipped with robotic manipulators. The BLG flake was mechanically torn using a sharp tip, for creating tDBLG superlattice. Detailed steps for sample fabrication, including the tear-and-stack process, are provided in SI Section 1.

Electrical measurements: Hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) was used as the top-gate dielectric, with a 300 nm thick layer of SiO_2 serving as the bottom-gate dielectric. The carrier density is n defined as $n = (\epsilon_0/e)[(\epsilon_{tg}(V_{tg} - V_{t0})/d_{tg}) + (\epsilon_{bg}(V_{bg} - V_{b0})/d_{bg})]$, where V_{tg} and V_{bg} represent the top and bottom gate voltages respectively. By simultaneously adjusting V_{tg} and V_{bg} while maintaining a constant displacement field D calculated using the expression $2D/\epsilon_0 = [(\epsilon_{tg}(V_{tg} - V_{t0})/d_{tg}) - (\epsilon_{bg}(V_{bg} - V_{b0})/d_{bg})]$, where, e is the electronic charge, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, and $\epsilon_{tg}(d_{tg})$ and $\epsilon_{bg}(d_{bg})$ indicate the dielectric constants (thicknesses) of the top and bottom gate dielectrics, respectively; V_{b0} and V_{t0} represent the gate voltage offsets required to reach the charge neutrality point (CNP). The thickness of the top-gate dielectric (d_{tg}) was determined from the progression of the CNP within the V_{tg} - V_{bg} phase space of sheet resistance (R_s), and this result was cross-verified through Hall measurements. Electrical measurements were performed using synchronized lock-in amplifiers with reference frequencies of 77.77 Hz and 17.77 Hz, both having input impedances significantly higher than R_s . No significant difference was observed between the two frequencies. The lock-in reference signal output was transformed into a current source using a high series-resistance ($\gg R_s$). Dual-channel DC source meters were employed to apply the gate voltages. The measurements were conducted within a closed-cycle cryostat, spanning a temperature range from 1.8 K to 300 K, with a vertical magnetic field range of ± 9 T.

Supporting information: The Supporting information (SI) is available for free from the publisher's website. SI contains the following sections:

1. Device fabrication method, and sample details.
2. Calculation of field-effect and Hall mobility.
3. $V_{xx}^{2\omega}$ vs n at different values of current bias (I_{ds}^{ω}).
4. First and second order transport data from another channel of sample A.
5. First and second order transport data from sample B.
6. First and second order transport data from sample C.
7. Estimation of second Harmonic generation efficiency and responsivity and comparison of figures-of-merits with literature

8. $V_{xy(x)}^{2\omega}/V_{xx}^{\omega^2}$ vs. σ^2 data from sample A
9. Scaling theory of NLER.
10. T -dependent scaling analysis from sample C.

Data availability statement: All data needed to evaluate the conclusions in the paper are included in the paper and/or the supporting information. All source data related to the findings in this study can be obtained from the authors. All the experimental data will be uploaded to the Zenodo repository upon publication.

Author contributions: T.A. and L.E.H. conceived the project. T.A. fabricated the samples, performed the measurements, analyzed the data and wrote the manuscript. B.Q.T. assisted in the experiments. T.T. and K.W. provided the hBN crystals. All authors discussed, commented on the paper. note: The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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References:

- [1] I. M. Lifshitz, Anomalies of electron characteristics of a metal in the high pressure region, *Sov. Phys. JEPT* **11**, 1130 (1960).
- [2] L. Van Hove, The Occurrence of Singularities in the Elastic Frequency Distribution of a Crystal, *Phys. Rev.* **89**, 1189 (1953).
- [3] G. Bastien, A. Gourgout, D. Aoki, A. Pourret, I. Sheikin, G. Seyfarth, J. Flouquet, and G. Knebel, Lifshitz Transitions in the Ferromagnetic Superconductor UCoGe, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **117**, 206401 (2016).
- [4] X. Shi et al., Enhanced superconductivity accompanying a Lifshitz transition in electron-doped FeSe monolayer, *Nat. Commun.* **8**, 14988 (2017).
- [5] C. Liu et al., Evidence for a Lifshitz transition in electron-doped iron arsenic superconductors at the onset of superconductivity, *Nat. Phys.* **6**, 419 (2010).
- [6] H. Zhou, L. Holleis, Y. Saito, L. Cohen, W. Huynh, C. L. Patterson, F. Yang, T. Taniguchi, K. Watanabe, and A. F. Young, Isospin magnetism and spin-polarized superconductivity in Bernal bilayer graphene, *Science* **375**, 774 (2022).
- [7] A. K. Geim and K. S. Novoselov, The rise of graphene, *Nat. Mater.* **6**, 183 (2007).
- [8] A. H. Castro Neto, F. Guinea, N. M. R. Peres, K. S. Novoselov, and A. K. Geim, The electronic properties of graphene, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **81**, 109 (2009).
- [9] E. McCann and M. Koshino, The electronic properties of bilayer graphene, *Rep. Prog. Phys.* **76**, 056503 (2013).
- [10] A. Varlet, D. Bischoff, P. Simonet, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, T. Ihn, K. Ensslin, M. Mucha-Kruczyński, and V. I. Fal'ko, Anomalous Sequence of Quantum Hall Liquids Revealing a Tunable Lifshitz Transition in Bilayer Graphene, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **113**, 116602 (2014).
- [11] A. M. Seiler, N. Jacobsen, M. Statz, N. Fernandez, F. Falorsi, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, Z. Dong, L. S. Levitov, and R. T. Weitz, Probing the tunable multi-cone band structure in Bernal bilayer graphene, *Nat. Commun.* **15**, 3133 (2024).
- [12] I. Brihuega, P. Mallet, H. González-Herrero, G. Trambly de Laissardière, M. M. Ugeda, L. Magaud, J. M. Gómez-Rodríguez, F. Ynduráin, and J.-Y. Veuillen, Unraveling the Intrinsic and Robust Nature of van Hove Singularities in Twisted Bilayer Graphene by Scanning Tunneling Microscopy and Theoretical Analysis, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **109**, 196802 (2012).
- [13] G. Li, A. Luican, J. M. B. Lopes dos Santos, A. H. Castro Neto, A. Reina, J. Kong, and E. Y. Andrei, Observation of Van Hove singularities in twisted graphene layers, *Nat. Phys.* **6**, 109 (2010).
- [14] S. Wu, Z. Zhang, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, and E. Y. Andrei, Chern insulators, van Hove singularities and topological flat bands in magic-angle twisted bilayer graphene, *Nat. Mater.* **20**, 488 (2021).
- [15] S. Xu et al., Tunable van Hove singularities and correlated states in twisted monolayer–bilayer graphene, *Nat. Phys.* **17**, 619 (2021).
- [16] R. Moriya, K. Kinoshita, J. A. Crosse, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, S. Masubuchi, P. Moon, M. Koshino, and T. Machida, Emergence of orbital angular moment at van Hove singularity in graphene/h-BN moiré superlattice, *Nat. Commun.* **11**, 5380 (2020).
- [17] R. Dutta, A. Ghosh, S. Mandal, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, H. R. Krishnamurthy, S. Banerjee, M. Jain, and A. Das, Electric Field-Tunable Superconductivity with Competing Orders in Twisted Bilayer Graphene near the Magic Angle, *ACS Nano* **19**, 5353 (2025).
- [18] R. Su, M. Kuri, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, and J. Folk, Superconductivity in twisted double bilayer graphene stabilized by WSe₂, *Nat. Mater.* **22**, 1332 (2023).
- [19] P. Knüppel, J. Zhu, Y. Xia, Z. Xia, Z. Han, Y. Zeng, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, J. Shan, and K. F. Mak, *Correlated States Controlled by Tunable van Hove Singularity in Moiré WSe₂*, arXiv:2406.03315.
- [20] Y.-W. Liu, J.-B. Qiao, C. Yan, Y. Zhang, S.-Y. Li, and L. He, Magnetism near half-filling of a Van Hove singularity in twisted graphene bilayer, *Phys. Rev. B* **99**, 201408 (2019).
- [21] I. Sodemann, Quantum Nonlinear Hall Effect Induced by Berry Curvature Dipole in Time-Reversal Invariant Materials, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **115**, (2015).

- [22] H. Isobe, S.-Y. Xu, and L. Fu, High-frequency rectification via chiral Bloch electrons, *Sci. Adv.* **6**, eaay2497 (2020).
- [23] Z. Z. Du, H.-Z. Lu, and X. C. Xie, Nonlinear Hall effects, *Nat. Rev. Phys.* **3**, 744 (2021).
- [24] Z. Z. Du, C. M. Wang, S. Li, H.-Z. Lu, and X. C. Xie, Disorder-induced nonlinear Hall effect with time-reversal symmetry, *Nat. Commun.* **10**, 3047 (2019).
- [25] M. Ramos et al., Unveiling Intrinsic Bulk Photovoltaic Effect in Atomically Thin ReS₂, *Nano Lett.* **24**, 14728 (2024).
- [26] T. Low, Y. Jiang, and F. Guinea, Topological currents in black phosphorus with broken inversion symmetry, *Phys. Rev. B* **92**, 235447 (2015).
- [27] M. Suárez-Rodríguez, F. D. Juan, I. Souza, M. Gobbi, F. Casanova, and L. E. Hueso, *Non-Linear Transport in Non-Centrosymmetric Systems: From Fundamentals to Applications*, arXiv:2412.05253.
- [28] P. He, G. K. W. Koon, H. Isobe, J. Y. Tan, J. Hu, A. H. C. Neto, L. Fu, and H. Yang, Graphene moiré superlattices with giant quantum nonlinearity of chiral Bloch electrons, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **17**, 378 (2022).
- [29] J. Duan, Y. Jian, Y. Gao, H. Peng, J. Zhong, Q. Feng, J. Mao, and Y. Yao, Giant Second-Order Nonlinear Hall Effect in Twisted Bilayer Graphene, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **129**, 186801 (2022).
- [30] Q. Ma et al., Observation of the nonlinear Hall effect under time-reversal-symmetric conditions, *Nature* **565**, 337 (2019).
- [31] Z. He and H. Weng, Giant nonlinear Hall effect in twisted bilayer WTe₂, *Npj Quantum Mater.* **6**, 1 (2021).
- [32] M. Huang et al., Giant nonlinear Hall effect in twisted bilayer WSe₂, *Natl. Sci. Rev.* **10**, nwac232 (2023).
- [33] M. Huang et al., Intrinsic Nonlinear Hall Effect and Gate-Switchable Berry Curvature Sliding in Twisted Bilayer Graphene, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **131**, 066301 (2023).
- [34] T. Ahmed, H. Varshney, B. Q. Tu, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, M. Gobbi, F. Casanova, A. Agarwal, and L. E. Hueso, Detecting Lifshitz Transitions Using Nonlinear Conductivity in Bilayer Graphene, *Small* **25**, 2501426 (2025).
- [35] S. Datta, S. Bhowmik, H. Varshney, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, A. Agarwal, and U. Chandni, Nonlinear Electrical Transport Unveils Fermi Surface Malleability in a Moiré Heterostructure, *Nano Lett.* **24**, 9520 (2024).
- [36] S. Sinha et al., Berry curvature dipole senses topological transition in a moiré superlattice, *Nat. Phys.* **18**, 765 (2022).
- [37] K. Kang, T. Li, E. Sohn, J. Shan, and K. F. Mak, Nonlinear anomalous Hall effect in few-layer WTe₂, *Nat. Mater.* **18**, 324 (2019).
- [38] P. A. Pantaleón, V. T. Phong, G. G. Naumis, and F. Guinea, Interaction-enhanced topological Hall effects in strained twisted bilayer graphene, *Phys. Rev. B* **106**, L161101 (2022).
- [39] C.-P. Zhang, J. Xiao, B. T. Zhou, J.-X. Hu, Y.-M. Xie, B. Yan, and K. T. Law, Giant nonlinear Hall effect in strained twisted bilayer graphene, *Phys. Rev. B* **106**, L041111 (2022).
- [40] M. Suárez-Rodríguez, Odd Nonlinear Conductivity under Spatial Inversion in Chiral Tellurium, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **132**, (2024).
- [41] P. He, H. Isobe, D. Zhu, C.-H. Hsu, L. Fu, and H. Yang, Quantum frequency doubling in the topological insulator Bi₂Se₃, *Nat. Commun.* **12**, 698 (2021).
- [42] Y. Cao, V. Fatemi, S. Fang, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, E. Kaxiras, and P. Jarillo-Herrero, Unconventional superconductivity in magic-angle graphene superlattices, *Nature* **556**, 43 (2018).
- [43] K. Roy, T. Ahmed, H. Dubey, T. P. Sai, R. Kashid, S. Maliakal, K. Hsieh, S. Shamim, and A. Ghosh, Number-Resolved Single-Photon Detection with Ultralow Noise van der Waals Hybrid, *Adv. Mater.* **30**, 1704412 (2018).
- [44] T. Ahmed, K. Roy, S. Kakkar, A. Pradhan, and A. Ghosh, Interplay of charge transfer and disorder in optoelectronic response in Graphene/hBN/MoS₂ van der Waals heterostructures, *2D Mater.* **7**, 025043 (2020).
- [45] C. Shen et al., Correlated states in twisted double bilayer graphene, *Nat. Phys.* **16**, 520 (2020).
- [46] Y. Wang, J. Herzog-Arbeitman, G. W. Burg, J. Zhu, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, A. H. MacDonald, B. A. Bernevig, and E. Tutuc, Bulk and edge properties of twisted double bilayer graphene, *Nat. Phys.* **18**, 1 (2022).
- [47] M. Koshino, Band structure and topological properties of twisted double bilayer graphene, *Phys. Rev. B* **99**, 235406 (2019).
- [48] Y. Cao et al., Correlated insulator behaviour at half-filling in magic-angle graphene superlattices, *Nature* **556**, 80 (2018).
- [49] Y. Wang, G. W. Burg, B. Lian, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, B. A. Bernevig, and E. Tutuc, Emergent Symmetry and Valley Chern Insulator in Twisted Double-Bilayer Graphene, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **133**, 246401 (2024).
- [50] P. C. Adak et al., Perpendicular electric field drives Chern transitions and layer polarization changes in Hofstadter bands, *Nat. Commun.* **13**, 7781 (2022).
- [51] F. K. de Vries et al., Kagome Quantum Oscillations in Graphene Superlattices, *Nano Lett.* **24**, 601 (2024).
- [52] M. Suárez-Rodríguez, B. Martín-García, W. Skowroński, K. Staszek, F. Calavalle, A. Fert, M. Gobbi, F. Casanova, and L. E. Hueso, Microscale Chiral Rectennas for Energy Harvesting, *Adv. Mater.* **36**, 2400729 (2024).